

Identifying policy areas for the transition of the transportation sector

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Abstract

Being the only energy sector where emissions are still at 1990 levels, the German transportation sector requires rapid decarbonization to achieve ambitious climate targets. Policy makers need to put the framework in place which enables and supports this transition. This work analyzes which policy areas should be targeted considering interactions with and implications for the entire energy system. The Global Energy System Model (GENeSYS-MOD) is used to compute 400 sensitivities which showcase the effectiveness of specific transport and energy system related policies. Shifting transportation demand to less energy and emission intensive modes or avoiding it in the first place shows the strongest effect on a number of key metrics. Primary energy consumption, emissions, and fleet size can all be reduced through a combination of electrification and shift towards public transport and long-distance trains. Carbon prices also showcase significant effects while further affecting the other energy sectors. The results suggest that in the intermediate term, modal shift and demand reduction can help with reducing transportation related emissions, while carbon prices are effective after 2040.

Keywords: Decarbonization, Energy Policy, Energy System Modeling, Energy Transition, GENeSYS-MOD, Transportation Sector Transition

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1. Introduction

Since the Paris agreement in 2015, emphasis around the globe has been put on reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions with the aim of keeping global warming below 1.5 °C or 2 °C compared to pre-industrial levels (UNFCCC, 2015). Yet, in its most recent report, the IPCC (2022) finds that global emissions kept rising until 2019 and that the current Nationally Determined Contributions (NCD) are insufficient if the 1.5 °C target is to be achieved without overshooting the emission budget. Therefore, additional measures are necessary to facilitate the decarbonization of the energy system, which is responsible for the majority of global GHG emissions (IPCC, 2022).

The transportation sector, as one of the energy sectors, is of particular interest, since it is the only sector in Europe and Germany with emissions still being higher or around 1990 levels (Umweltbundesamt, 2022a; European Commission. Directorate General for Mobility and Transport., 2021). Currently relying heavily on fossil fuels (i.e. oil), the future transportation system will likely see more electrified options if GHG emissions are to be reduced. This, however, puts additional stress on the energy system, as the electricity required to power vehicles and trains needs to be produced through renewable energy sources and is also required for the decarbonization of other sectors like industry or buildings. Therefore, the field of energy system modeling experienced rapid growth over the last decade, motivated by the realization that an integrated analysis of the entire energy system is key for a future sector coupled energy system.

One apparent issue when analyzing future systems, no matter the domain, is the uncertainty that comes with it. Predicting the future is impossible yet trying to is necessary to gain insights into interactions and dependencies of the system of interest. The energy system will undergo a significant transformation in the upcoming years to achieve the targeted climate goals and future (uncertain) developments will have a strong influence on the shape of the transformation. Today, policy and decision makers need to put the regulatory framework in place which will facilitate this transformation, relying on analyses and predictions on the effectiveness of their methods. And yet, even the most robust approaches when it comes to dealing with uncertainty will fail in predicting shock events which we can currently observe. The Covid-19 pandemic as well as the Russian invasion of Ukraine both have massive short term implications on the energy system (IEA, 2022a,b) deeming most past model calculations incorrect. Therefore, developing an understanding of different energy system components and actors becomes even more important to be able to adapt to new situations while still being on the path of reducing GHG emissions.

Consequently, when analyzing possible futures and developments of the energy and transportation sector it is imperative to understand how the system is affected by different parameters which today are still uncertain. This work aims to answer the question of what are the impacts of key (uncertain) energy and transportation system parameters on the success of the German energy and mobility transition and which areas policy makers should target to generate the biggest impact. The Global Energy System Model (GENeSYS-MOD) is applied to analyze a pathway of the German energy system until 2050 and in a second step complemented by a multitude of sensitivities highlighting the effect and leverage of specific input parameters on energy and transportation system related key performance indicators (KPIs).

The following part of this paper presents the status quo of the German energy and transportation transition and policies (Section 2), as well as relevant literature (Section 2.1). Section 3 gives an overview of the applied model, methodology, and further assumptions, followed by Section 4 describing data sources and requirements. Following, Section 5 explores the results and discusses its implications as well as shortcomings of the methodology. Lastly, Section 6 concludes by stating policy implications and providing a brief outlook of future research needs.

2. German policy situation of the energy and mobility transition

In June 2021, the German parliament agreed on an updated climate protection law (german: *Klimaschutzgesetz*) which increased the GHG reduction targets to 65% in 2030, 88% in 2040 (both compared to 1990 levels) and GHG neutrality by 2045 (BMWK, 2022). In addition, sectoral emission reduction targets were also adjusted putting the burden on each sector to contribute to the overall reduction. And while overall emissions decreased by more than 35% between 1990 and 2019 (Umweltbundesamt, 2022a), it seems unlikely that Germany can achieve its ambitious climate targets (BMU, 2021; Agora Energiewende, 2022).

The transportation sector is the only sector in Germany, where, despite climate efforts and targets, GHG emissions in 2019 were still around 1990 levels (Umweltbundesamt, 2022b). The aforementioned sectoral emission reduction targets, however, demand a 48% reduction until 2030, which effectively has to be achieved within one decade (Umweltbundesamt, 2022b). To achieve the target of 85 Mt CO₂e, the German federal environmental agency (UBA) proposed a variety of action blocks which target the regulatory, infrastructural, and economical framework (UBA, 2022). Most of these blocks address road transportation since cars, trucks, and buses are responsible for 96% of total domestic transportation emissions (Eurostat, 2022).

One often mentioned cornerstone of the successful decarbonization of the transportation sector is electric mobility. As of April 2022, about 700,000 cars in Germany are battery electric vehicles (BEVs) (Statista, 2022a), making up less than 1.5% of total number of passenger cars (Statista, 2022b). As a result, the declared target of 15 million BEVs by 2030 implies a substantial increase in sales as well as investments into charging infrastructure. Assuming 3.5 million newly registered cars per year, similar to pre-pandemic levels, almost every second vehicle would have to be electric in order to achieve the ambitious goal - a goal which according to a study by the Wuppertal Institut might still be insufficient to achieve the set climate targets (Koska and Jansen, 2022).

Naturally, electric mobility also affects other modes of transportation but is either already widely deployed (i.e. rail) or technologically not mature enough yet to be considered as a viable option within the next decade (e.g. freight transportation). In the latter case, hydrogen and synthetic fuels could play a crucial role in defossilizing the transportation sector. While the overall efficiency of hydrogen is much worse compared to the direct use of electricity due to energy losses in the conversion process, its application in specific areas like heavy duty freight transportation or aviation could assist with the overall transformation (Staffell et al., 2019). However, with large-scale renewable hydrogen not being commercially available yet (Pareek et al., 2020), future cost and efficiency developments will play a crucial role determining the viability of hydrogen as a fuel.

Costs of fossil fuels also play a substantial role in the configuration of the transportation sector. Extraction, processing, and transportation of gasoline or diesel make up a sizeable share of the prices at gas station. The Russian invasion of Ukraine caused a significant increase in oil and gas prices, causing the diesel price in Germany to surpass 2€/l. But an even higher share consists of taxes for energy, value added, and carbon emissions (ADAC, 2022), which in the case of diesel is further subsidized. Among other things, removing subsidies for fossil fuels and increasing the carbon price are measures which are cited to enable the transformation of the transportation sector (UBA, 2022; Agora Verkehrswende, 2018).

2.1. Review of Relevant Literature

Various studies and articles exist which analyze either the future German transportation sector in a decarbonized energy system or policies on how to achieve it. With the updated climate targets set

by the new German government in 2021, multiple long-term scenario studies analyzing the pathways towards GHG neutrality in 2045 were published in the past months (BCG, 2021; Krail et al., 2021; Luderer et al., 2021; Prognos et al., 2021; Dena, 2021). While scenarios and assumptions differ, all paint a picture of quick decarbonization of all sectors, including the transportation sector which is rapidly electrified. Since all studies target full decarbonization until 2045, strong assumptions on transportation demand were made.

In a comprehensive overview of multi-sector energy transition scenarios for Germany, Naegler et al. (2021) show that for 26 scenarios by different studies aiming for at least 90% GHG reduction until 2050, BEVs dominate road transportation in 2050 while results for freight transportation often lack in degree of detail. In general, future technology diversity in the transportation sector is projected to be much more pronounced than today. Bartholdsen et al. (2019) and Löffler et al. (2022) both analyze the transportation sector as part of a decarbonized energy system. Electrification is found to be a cornerstone of the transformation of the transportation system, coupled with high amounts of renewable energies. Additionally, Löffler et al. (2022) find that demand reductions show high potentials for overall emission reductions. Recently, Ehrenberger et al. (2021) provided scenarios which analyze the emissions of the transportation sector until 2040 given three different scenarios which assume different levels of technological and regulatory development. They conclude that heavy electrification and decarbonization of the electricity sector is required for GHG reductions in the transportation sector, yet none of the scenarios reached GHG neutrality despite strong assumptions (Ehrenberger et al., 2021). Similarly, Winkler and Mocanu (2020) find that technological development is important to decarbonize road transportation which will remain the most important mode of transportation. The authors point out that measures which reduce transportation or shift it towards more efficient modes have the highest effects on reducing transportation emissions.

Furthermore, Wicki et al. (2019) highlight that policy acceptance does not necessarily depend on the type of policy but rather the context. In their experiment the authors find that reduction in public transport prices and income tax, coupled with an increase in fuel prices and taxes and eliminating fossil fuel subsidies shows high support. Peiseler and Cabrera Serrenho (2022) show that current policies do not make full use of the potential of electric vehicles and propose ways on how to adjust these policies in order to facilitate the decarbonization of road transportation.

All of these findings tie into the A-S-I approach (Avoid-Shift-Improve) which was developed in the early 90s in Germany which "... serves as a way to structure policy measures to reduce the environmental impact of transport and thereby improve the quality of life in cities" (GIZ, 2019). *Avoid* refers to reducing demand for transportation by either better transport or city planning. *Shift* focuses on improving individual trip efficiency by shifting transport from the most energy consuming and polluting modes of transportation to more environmentally friendly ones. Lastly, *improve* targets vehicle efficiency as well as the entire value chain of fuel generation. These categories play an important role on the shape and effectiveness of transportation policies and the discussion in Section 5.3 will analyze which policies and respective areas show the strongest effects.

Overall, most of the literature focuses either on the transportation sector and related policies or on the energy system as a whole with insufficient degree of detail when it comes to transportation. This work tries to bridge this gap and highlight policy effects in the transportation sector while keeping interactions with the rest of the energy system in mind. Further, all data and model source-code is publicly available, contributing to open science and allowing other researchers to reproduce the findings and further contribute to this topic.

3. Methodology

For the present work, the Global Energy System Model (GENeSYS-MOD) is being used as a tool to analyze future pathways of the German transportation and energy sector. The following sections briefly introduce the framework, highlight improvements made to GENeSYS-MOD for this study as well as describe the sensitivity analysis approach.

3.1. GENeSYS-MOD and model setup

GENeSYS-MOD is an open-source energy system model which is tailored towards long-term energy system transition pathways and based on the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS).¹ Since its first publication in 2017 (Löffler et al., 2017), it has been applied in numerous case-studies and projects (e.g. Germany (Bartholdsen et al., 2019), Europe (Hainsch et al., 2021), South Africa (Hanto et al., 2021) or Japan (Burandt, 2021)). With the different energy sectors becoming increasingly connected in the future energy systems, due to sector coupling and electrification, GENeSYS-MOD analyses these sector interactions by simultaneously optimizing investments, energy generation, and dispatch while considering regional particularities and possible climate policies. Figure 1 illustrates a simplified structure of GENeSYS-MOD.

Figure 1: Simplified representation of inputs, model components, and outputs of GENeSYS-MOD

The work presented in this article builds upon previous iterations of GENeSYS-MOD which analyze the German energy transition under specific scenario assumptions (Bartholdsen et al., 2019) and highlight chances and barriers of said transition (Löffler et al., 2022). Especially the sensitivity analysis carried out in the second article is extended now to the transportation sector and described in more detail in Section 3.3. Germany is split into its 16 federal states and the analysis is carried out starting in 2015 until 2050 in 5 year steps. The year 2017 is added and together with 2015 and 2020 serves as a base year for calibration purposes. With the year 2020 being dominated by the Covid pandemic, the effects are also reflected in the energy system in the form of reduced demands

¹For further information on GENeSYS-MOD including a documentation, quick-start guide, and a sample data set, the reader is referred to: <https://git.tu-berlin.de/genesysmod/genesys-mod-public>

for all energy services. Nevertheless, it is included in the analysis due to its implications on the subsequent years. Since investments, generation, and dispatch are optimized simultaneously for all years, the sub-annual resolution has to be reduced to not run into computational challenges. A timeseries-clustering algorithm, described in Gerbaulet and Lorenz (2017) and Burandt et al. (2019), was applied which reduced the timeseries to every 74th hour, resulting in 118 time steps per year which take daily and seasonal variations of demand and generation into account.

3.2. Improvements to GENeSYS-MOD

Since its first iteration in 2017, no structural changes have been made to the transportation sector in GENeSYS-MOD. Therefore, the degree of detail of the transportation sector, specific functionalities, and usability were updated for the present work to allow for more in-depth analyses. Originally, transportation demand was split between freight and passenger transportation with a number of different modes (i.e. road, rail, and air/ship for passenger/freight respectively) and corresponding technologies for each of the two. For the present work, public transport in the form of buses and short-distance trains was added to the modal types to better illustrate the different options for passenger transportation, especially in urban areas. Initially, it was also planned to disaggregate road freight transportation into light-duty and heavy-duty vehicles as they serve two different purposes as well as offering different technological possibilities. However, vehicles under 20,000 kg maximum weight, which light-duty vehicles belong to, only make up 2.7% of total road transportation according to the Federal Motor Transport Authority (Kraftfahrtbundesamt, 2021). With road transportation therefore being heavily dominated by heavy duty vehicles in terms of transportation amount and, thus, also emissions, this mode was left untouched. Other modes of transportation which are not energy dependent, like biking or walking, lack direct interaction with the energy system and are therefore not considered. Assumptions about these modes are made and taken into account when determining the overall transportation demand, however. Figure 2 illustrates the technology landscape and demand structure of the updated transportation sector in GENeSYS-MOD.

Next, the structure of the implementation of BEVs was updated. Originally, BEVs were treated like overhead-powered trains, meaning that the electricity required to fuel the vehicles was produced at the same time it was consumed. As a result, the flexibility potential of BEVs was underestimated. With the new implementation, all battery electric vehicles (i.e. cars, trucks, and buses) are connected to a storage unit which can be charged at any time and provide the required electricity at a later point in time. It is noteworthy that for the current work charging patterns are subject to the optimization and can therefore differ from currently observed charging behaviour which is mainly consumer determined (Element Energy, 2019).

Another change in design was implemented with respect to how transportation demands are considered in the model. In the previous iterations, two demands were specified (freight and passenger) and for each demand a modal split was defined for each year, stating how much of the respective demand had to be covered by which mode of transportation. Within these modes, single technologies were then able to contribute to the required modal split and consequently demand. This formulation had the drawback that if demand for a specific mode of transportation was to be altered, all other modes were also affected or at least had to be considered. With the new formulation, each mode of transportation has its own demand which can be modified independently, making scenario analyses and data acquisition and implementation more user-friendly. In addition, a flexible demand for passenger and freight transportation was added which can be covered by all technologies which belong to passenger or freight transportation respectively. This allows for more flexibility in the

Figure 2: Structure of updated transportation sector in GENeSYS-MOD

future transportation system, where the exact specification of the modal split might be uncertain. Lastly, more possibilities for the user to directly input data are provided. While the initial implementation of input parameters is still available if desired, the new version allows for directly inserting values for typical transport and vehicle parameters like annual vehicle driving distance, occupancy/load factor, fuel consumption per 100 km, or vehicle purchasing cost. While all of the mentioned parameters were already included in GENeSYS-MOD, they were part of more complex parameters and, as a result, not easily accessible for scenario or result analyses. The new implementation allows users to use more intuitive values which might also be easier to find data for, while keeping the old version in place.

3.3. Sensitivity Analysis

The objective of this work is to highlight the effect and leverage specific transport related policies have on the overall German energy transition. While it is agreed upon that the future energy system will have to look significantly different compared to today if climate goals are to be achieved, opinions differ on what this transformation will have to look like (Clack et al., 2017; Brown et al., 2018; Schill et al., 2018). With models being unable to predict the future, their strength lies rather in the comparison of results and the resulting generation of insights than in the provision of single numbers (Huntington et al., 1982). As a result, uncertainties in the future energy system need to be considered when analyzing such a system, especially when communicating the results to policy and decision makers.

Several methodologies exist to address uncertainty in modeling. The most common ones either focus on directly addressing it through stochastic modeling (Birge and Louveaux, 2011; Burandt, 2021), applying limited foresight to the model (Gerbaulet et al., 2019; Löffler et al., 2019), or altering

uncertain input parameters in the form of scenarios or a sensitivity analysis (Pfenninger et al., 2014; Hainsch et al., 2021; Löffler et al., 2022). In particular, sensitivity analysis describes the approach of changing single input parameters and observing the models behaviour, being able to directly attribute changes in the results to the parameter of interest. The disadvantage, however, consists of ignoring interactions between multiple different (uncertain) factors which are important in the real system (Ferretti et al., 2016). In this study, the methodology of exploratory sensitivity analysis will be used to quantify the effects of four different factors on the overall energy system and the transportation sector in particular. The aforementioned shortcoming will be kept in mind for the analysis and interpretation of the results, which nonetheless provide valuable insights into the effects and leverages of policies targeting the transportation sector.

The four factors which will be analyzed are the following: carbon price, transportation demand, hydrogen generation efficiency and costs, and modal shift. Carbon prices or taxes are widely regarded as a suitable tool to facilitate the low-carbon transition of energy systems (Baranzini et al., 2017; IPCC, 2018), yet have to be treated with caution in terms of magnitude and uniformity (Verbruggen and Brauers, 2020). Reducing transportation demand in terms of passenger or ton kilometer is another major lever to facilitate the low-carbon energy system transformation (Löffler et al., 2022), yet not analyzed as extensively in the energy system modeling literature as, for example, technological solutions (Dominković et al., 2018). Hydrogen has been, and is, considered by some as a significant driver in defossilizing the transportation sector (Berry et al., 1996; Chapman et al., 2019; Staffell et al., 2019). However, costs and efficiencies are prominently mentioned as limiting factors (Chapman et al., 2019; Staffell et al., 2019). Lastly, shifting transportation from energy and carbon intensive modes to lesser ones offers the possibility to reduce emissions and energy demand while at the same time providing the same amount of transportation services (Shah et al., 2021).

For this study, a base-case is modeled and used as a reference, taking into account current projections, phase-out targets, price and demand developments, etc. In a second step, parameters which can be attributed to one of the four aforementioned factors are slightly altered one by one to analyze their impact on the future energy and transportation system. 100 sensitivities are computed for each case, leading to a total of 400 deviations from the base case. Table 1 showcases which parameters were altered as well as the ranges for each of the four cases. Generally, maximum and minimum values for the parameters consist of the parameter's base value multiplied or divided by two, respectively. The exception of this rule is transportation demand, where due to its large effect a factor of 1.5 was chosen. Four big energy scenario studies conducted in the past years in Germany project the transportation demand to grow up to 10% until 2030 for passenger transportation and up to 20% for freight transportation (Luderer et al., 2021; Prognos et al., 2021; Krail et al., 2021; BCG, 2021). Therefore, using 1.5 as the sensitivity factor allows a more detailed representation of the relevant interval while still allowing to analyze a wide range of values. The 100 sensitivities per case are linearly distributed between one and the respective factor. Since the year 2030 is of particular interest due to several climate policies, the sensitivity factor is fully applied from 2030 on with half its effect being applied in 2025.

Table 1: Analyzed sensitivities, corresponding model parameters and intervals of values for the year 2030.

	Parameters	Min	Default	Max	Factor
Carbon price	Emission cost	40 €/ton	80 €/ton	160 €/ton	2
Transportation demand	Total demand for freight and passenger transportation	66.66%	100%	150%	1.5
Hydrogen costs and efficiencies	Efficiencies for hydrogen generating technologies	50%	67%	80%	2
	Costs of hydrogen imports	18€/kg	9€/kg	4.5€/kg	
Modal shift	Share of flexible transportation demand compared to overall transportation demand	3%	6%	12%	2

4. Data

For the analysis carried out in this study, data for various parameters had to be updated with the main reason being twofold: First, the expansion of the transportation sector by public transport required extensive data research on techno-economic vehicle parameters as well as regionally disaggregated demands for buses and short-distance trains. Second, the inclusion of 2020 as a reference year demanded the inclusion of energy capacities, generation, and demand not only for the transportation but for all energy sectors. Since the present study builds upon Bartholdsen et al. (2019) and Löffler et al. (2022), the reader is referred to these two articles for information on all data not described in the following sections.

4.1. Public Transport

Transportation demand for public transport was taken from the Federal Office of Statistics together with the occupancy factor for each German federal state (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2022). In conjunction with efficiencies for electric, hydrogen, and diesel buses (Infoportal NRW, 2021a,b; Berliner Morgenpost, 2018), the efficiency per passenger kilometer per federal state can be calculated. Vehicle purchasing costs for buses are also taken from Infoportal NRW (2021b). Similarly, for short distance trains purchasing costs (Berliner Morgenpost, 2012; Frankfurter Rundschau, 2019), consumption (Deiters, 2009), and the mentioned occupancy factors are used to compute the necessary parameters.

4.2. Reference year calibration and demand projections

The inclusion of 2020 as a reference year requires data on demands for all sectors. However, with the Covid pandemic breaking out in the early months of the year, energy and transportation demand saw a substantial decrease compared to expectations (Mofijur et al., 2021; IEA, 2020). This atypical behaviour comes with two challenges: On the one hand, energy system models are not calibrated taking such drastic shocks into account and, as a result, need to be constraint heavily to represent these situations adequately. On the other hand, data for all sectors and federal states is not fully available yet which usually leads to assumptions being made based on projections and similar developments. Since there is no prior experience on an event of such scale, these assumptions have to be treated with caution.

Power production per technology was taken from BDEW (2022) while demand for heating and industry was adjusted by the same factor due to a lack of available data. Transportation demand for 2019 was taken from the European Commission. Directorate General for Mobility and Transport. (2021) and adjusted for 2020 based on a report of Transport (2021). Demand projections for up to 2045 were adopted from the Ariadne Report which analyzes pathways for Germany’s decarbonization until 2045 (Luderer et al., 2021).

5. Results

This section presents and analyzes the main results. First, the base case results will be highlighted describing the basis on which the sensitivities build upon. The second part focuses on the sensitivities and shed light on how sensitive the model results react by analyzing and comparing six energy and transportation sector related KPIs.

5.1. Base case results

The results of the base case describe a pathway towards a highly decarbonized German energy system with small amounts of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions left in 2050, thus missing the proposed target of no GHG-emissions by 2045. Figure 3 shows that the electricity sector is the quickest to be decarbonized, while transportation and buildings are responsible for the remaining emissions in 2045 and 2050. This rapid decarbonization of the electricity sector is key, since non-fossil options in the other sectors mainly rely on electricity which needs to be produced through renewable energies for an effective decarbonization. Overall, the target of 65% reduced GHG emissions in 2030 compared to 1990 is achieved. The respective carbon budgets, derived from the global carbon budgets stated by the IPCC (2021) AR6 WG1 report, are also depicted, representing a 66% chance to keep global warming below 1.5 °C and 2 °C, respectively. Since the stated budgets represent a global limit, the country budget for Germany was determined by the share of population for the purpose of this illustration. Figure 3 clearly shows that even as quick of a decarbonization as in the base case fails to come close to the 1.5 °C target, while still achieving the 2 °C target.

This reduction in emissions is facilitated by a substantial increase in electricity production which, in turn, is caused by high degrees of electrification of the residential, industrial, and transportation sector. Contrary, primary energy consumption is reduced, with the reason being higher efficiencies of electricity-consuming technologies compared to their fossil-fueled alternatives. Figure 4 illustrates electricity production and primary energy consumption in the base case. Compared to 2015, electricity production almost doubles until 2050 with wind onshore, wind offshore, and photovoltaic (PV) contributing almost equally and supplemented by small amounts of bio-energy and hydropower. Wind onshore, and to a degree PV, is expanded rapidly in the early modeling periods, followed by wind offshore which takes off in the later periods. Fossil fuels, on the other hand, are quickly being phased out with coal and natural gas becoming irrelevant after 2040 due to their emission intensity and cost-disadvantages compared to renewables, while all nuclear power plants are shut down in 2022 following governmental plans. The declared political target of at least 80% renewable power generation in 2030 is achieved.

Figure 3: Annual emissions per sector (bars) and cumulative emissions (line) in the base case. Source: Own illustration.

Figure 4: Primary energy consumption (left) and power production (right) in the base case. Source: Own illustration.

Crucially, no new fossil capacities are build as can be seen in Figure 5 which shows total and new capacities per year. While fossil capacities slowly disappear due to their expiration of lifetime, wind and PV capacities are quickly expanded by an annual rate of 16 GW combined until 2030 and up to 32 GW until 2040. Storage options become important in 2035 with lithium-ion batteries complementing the already existing pumped hydro storage.

Figure 5: Total installed capacities (top) and new capacities (bottom) in the base case. Source: Own illustration.

Lastly, the results of the transportation sector will be highlighted due to their significance for the sensitivity analysis in the second part of this chapter. Figure 6 illustrates the technologies and their respective transportation volumes for both passenger and freight transportation. For the passenger part, a strong shift towards BEVs can be observed with about 20% of motorized private transport in 2030 and almost 100% in 2050. The 2030 value equates to almost 10 million BEVs which significantly misses the target of 15 million. However, with 20 million BEVs in 2035, this mark is missed only by a few years. Another trend for passenger transportation is the increased significance of public transport. Both buses and short distance trains provide almost all of the flexible transportation demand, highlighting their higher cost-effectiveness compared to cars. A similar trend can be observed in freight transportation where rail becomes more important for the same reasons. Since battery trucks are a non-factor, road freight transportation shifts towards less carbon intensity by first introducing plug-in vehicles fueled by bio-diesel and later H2-trucks replacing traditional diesel trucks.

Figure 6: Passenger (left) and freight (right) transportation in the base case. Source: Own illustration.

5.2. Sensitivity results

As described in Section 3.3, four different cases are considered as sensitivities: *Carbon price*, *Demand*, *Hydrogen*, and *Modal shift*. For each of these cases, 100 sensitivities were calculated varying corresponding input parameters around the base case values (see Table 1 for an overview of the affected parameters and ranges). To allow for a comprehensive comparison of such a large number of model results, six KPIs are defined which will likely be important in the future energy and transportation sector:

- Total transport related primary energy consumption
- Total electricity production
- Total amount of transport related emissions
- Specific emissions of cars
- Number of cars
- Total hydrogen production and import

Starting with electricity production and primary energy consumption in the transportation sector, the results of the sensitivities are depicted in Figure 7 grouped by sensitivity case. The cases *Carbon price* and *Demand* show the highest effect on electricity production with *Hydrogen* and *Modal shift* being less significant. Naturally, a change of carbon price does not only affect the transportation sector but also all other areas of energy generation directly, which is why the effect on power generation is more pronounced. However, the carbon price does not seem to have nearly as

much of an effect on the primary energy consumption in the transportation sector, even though the transformation of the sector towards more electricity and less oil comes with significant reductions of primary energy demand. Here, the effects of *Demand* are the strongest, spanning a wide range of required energy, which is one of the reasons why the sensitivity range for *Demand* was chosen to be smaller compared to the others. The initial increase in primary energy consumption for high demand sensitivities is explained by the increase in demand leading to more energy demand. In the later periods, however, efficiency improvements and electrification dominate the effect of increased demand which leads to the overall reduction of primary energy consumption. A 50% increase in projected transportation demand by 2030 might very well be too extreme and should only be treated as a modeling decision, with the relative changes being more relevant rather than the absolute numbers. Interestingly, *Modal shift* has the second highest effect on primary energy showing that higher shares of public transport can help with reducing the energy demand of the transportation sector.

Figure 7: Electricity production (top) and primary energy consumption in the transportation sector (bottom) for all sensitivity cases. The color range represents the factor of the respective sensitivity.

When taking a look at the emissions (Figure 8), a similar picture can be observed. Overall transport related emissions are most affected by *Demand*, followed by *Carbon price* and *Modal shift* with *Hydrogen* having almost no effect at all. The strong reaction to *Demand* can be attributed to the high shares of fossil fuels still prevalent in 2030 and, thus, the additional demand having to be covered by fossil technologies. Another interesting effect is that, while higher (or lower) CO₂ prices lead to less (or more) emissions towards the end of the modeling period, *Modal shift* affects mostly the intermediate years. This can be explained by some modes of transportation (i.e. rail transportation) already being electrified to a high degree and, thus, encouraging a switch from other modes to rail transportation given the possibility. In terms of specific emissions of cars, however, only

Carbon price shows meaningful deviations compared to the base case, especially when considering lower values (light orange).

Figure 8: Annual transport emissions (top) and specific emissions of cars (bottom) for all sensitivity cases. The color range represents the factor of the respective sensitivity.

Lastly, the electric vehicle stock (cars) and hydrogen production are considered. Figure 9 highlights that *Demand*, again, has the highest effect on total number of electric cars, since the number of vehicles is directly correlated to the demand for private road transport. However, *Modal shift* also shows a significant influence on this KPI and highlights that a slight shift towards more public transport can have strong effects on the number of vehicles. A carbon price can change the speed of transition towards electric vehicles in the intermediate years, while *Hydrogen* has no deviations at all with both hydrogen and electric vehicles being aggregated for the figure. However, even when separating hydrogen vehicles and BEVs the results show little to no difference suggesting that BEVs are by far superior in terms of energy consumption and economic efficiency. In terms of overall hydrogen production, *Hydrogen* has the highest effect together with *Carbon price* while *Demand* and especially *Modal shift* show less significant results. This suggests that the other energy sectors, especially industry and heating, are more likely to affect hydrogen production, since the two dominant cases not only affect the transportation sector but all sectors. *Demand*, in turn, has much less effect on hydrogen production, even though it showed the strongest effect in most other cases, leading to the conclusion that the role of hydrogen in the transportation sector is quite robust (see Figure 6).

5.3. Discussion of Model Results and Limitations

The results of the base case describe a pathway which heavily decarbonizes the German energy sector. While some climate targets are achieved (i.e. 80% renewable power generation and 65%

Figure 9: Number of electric vehicles (top) and hydrogen production (bottom) for all sensitivity cases. The color range represents the factor of the respective sensitivity.

GHG emission reduction in 2030), others are missed by a substantial margin like, for example, the 1.5 °C climate target, 15 million electric vehicles in 2030 or reaching climate neutrality by 2045. The national carbon budgets associated with the 1.5 °C or 2 °C climate target, however, can be calculated using different methodologies and the chosen values are on the lower end of the spectrum (Hainsch et al., 2021). Electricity generation needs to be decarbonized quickly to facilitate the electrification of the other energy sectors and, at the same time, expanded significantly in terms of renewable energies to be able to provide the increased demand. New fossil generation capacities are not required which is a result of the integrated optimization recognizing that new investments would quickly become stranded. Shortsighted decision-making, however, can lead to these investments which should be avoided by considering their long-term effects (Löffler et al., 2019). Policy and decision makers should therefore not neglect the long term effects of their decisions which could lead to path dependencies and slow down the speed of transformation.

Similarly to the electricity sector, the transportation sector is quickly transformed towards less carbon intensive technologies in the form of electric vehicles or biofuel based ones where direct electrification is not an option. Rail transportation and public transport prove to be more energy and cost efficient than road transportation coupled with easier electrification. Hydrogen is used significantly in freight transportation, where batteries are not as efficient.

The sensitivity analysis highlights that transportation demand has the overall largest effect on most of the considered KPIs, directly affecting primary energy demand, emissions, and vehicle stock to a large degree. Policies belonging to the *avoid* category of the A-S-I approach therefore seem to be the most effective tool in achieving the decarbonization of the transportation sector and should be a point of emphasis. The *Avoid* category relies significantly on societal support and willingness to

adapt which some studies found is present given the correct implementation and communication of measures (Cherry et al., 2018; Schmitz et al., 2019).

A more pronounced modal shift also has a strong effect on number of vehicles, especially when considering that the chosen range of the sensitivity is much lower than of *Demand*. Moreover, focusing on the *Shift* category of A-S-I can help with reducing emissions in the intermediate term, since rail transportation is already mostly electrified. With the electricity sector most likely leading the way in terms of decarbonization, shifting transportation demand from cars to trains can lead to a reduction of emissions even before the large-scale deployment of electric vehicles. The increased electricity demand would be comparably low as illustrated in Figure 7.

With respect to carbon prices, the results show relevant results across almost all KPIs. The strongest effects which can be observed on hydrogen production and electricity generation are partially influenced by the effects of a carbon price on the other sectors. Within the transportation sector, the speed of BEV rollout is influenced by higher or lower carbon prices and, as a result, sectoral emissions. The results of the *Carbon price* case can similarly be interpreted for a possible reduction of subsidies for fossil fuels, since both affect fuel costs of vehicles. With the current diesel subsidies of 18.4 cents per liter (UBA, 2022), removing the privilege would have roughly the increase in prices as a carbon price increase of 70 €/ton, making this option a simple to execute and precise measure. Lastly, the *Hydrogen* case has the least impact across all KPIs with only hydrogen production being affected notably. This could lead to two suggestions: On the one hand, the basic assumptions for future development of hydrogen technologies are too pessimistic, such that even a massive improvement in efficiency and costs does not make hydrogen-vehicles the superior option. On the other hand, hydrogen could be limited to specific areas like trucks and buses, as can be seen in the base case in Figure 6, being a robust solution for the decarbonization of these areas without many alternatives.

Despite all these findings, some shortcomings of the present analysis and model are important to be mentioned in order to adequately interpret the results. The model takes the perspective of a central planner while in reality, especially in the transportation sector, individuals make decisions which do not align necessarily with climate goals. Particularly important is the modal choice which can not be depicted realistically by the model since, in reality, non techno-economical factors (e.g. weather, time of travel, availability of vehicles) play a significant role. With demands being an exogenous parameter, rebound effects of energy efficiency improvements are not considered which is especially important for the *Improve* category of the A-S-I approach. The use of exploratory sensitivity analysis neglects that changing one parameter could have implications on other input parameters. Moreover, the full effect of the sensitivities taking effect in 2030 can lead to extreme and possibly unrealistic results, especially when it comes to the *Demand* sensitivity. This is important to keep in mind when analyzing the results. Finally, the linear nature of the model requires simplifications of interactions in order to be computationally feasible.

6. Conclusions and Policy Implications

This article analyzes the effect and leverage of specific areas policy and decision makers can target on the overall energy and transportation sector transformation. With the European and German transportation sector being the only energy sector where GHG emissions are still around 1990 levels, policy makers need to define the framework to effectively and rapidly reduce emissions. At the same time, interactions with the entire energy system need to be kept in mind which becomes increasingly complex due to sector coupling and electrification.

The open source Global Energy System Model (GENeSYS-MOD) is used for the analysis. A base scenario is calculated showcasing a possible pathway for the German low-carbon energy system transformation until 2050. With increasing amounts of renewable energy sources and replacement of fossil technologies by cleaner ones, GHG emissions can effectively be reduced. The future transportation sector is dominated by electric vehicles wherever economically feasible, while large parts of freight transportation rely on a combination of hydrogen and biofuels.

A calculation of 400 sensitivities which deviate from the base case reveal that some areas have stronger effects on the future energy and transportation sector than others. A reduction of transportation demand strongly influences the amount of primary energy, emissions, and fleet size while also affecting electricity generation and hydrogen production in meaningful ways. Therefore, focusing on policies which eliminate the need for transportation, e.g. by structuring cities more efficiently, should be of high priority for policy makers.

Modal shift suggests to be another effective way of impacting primary energy consumption and fleet size. Moreover, shifting transportation from road to rail, specifically, can lead to significant emission reductions in early years. Rail transportation is already electrified to a large degree which coupled with renewable electricity can reduce transport emissions before large scale deployment of electric vehicles. Incentivizing this shift should be another priority for policy makers by making public transport and long-distance trains more attractive or facilitating multi-modal transportation. Approaches like the recently introduced "9€-Ticket" showed a significant increase in the use rail transportation but also highlighted the need for substantial investments into infrastructure in order to accommodate rising numbers of passengers (Tagesschau, 2022).

Significant effects can also be observed if carbon prices are altered. Especially emissions, electricity, and hydrogen production react sensitive towards a change in carbon prices. However, this can also be attributed to effects in other energy sectors, as a higher carbon price also applies to the industry and buildings sector. Nevertheless, carbon prices and also the reduction of fossil fuel subsidies are a suitable tool to accelerate the shift towards electrified transportation. Changes in hydrogen costs and efficiencies, on the other hand, show little impact in the transportation sector which suggests a robust role of hydrogen in freight transportation but little to no application for private motorized transport.

This article has highlighted which areas policy makers should target in order to set the framework for a rapid decarbonization of the transportation sector. Transport related emissions need to be reduced quickly if climate goals are to be achieved and this work showcases that high shares of renewable energies and electrification of transportation are major pillars in achieving said goals. Policies which address the areas of avoiding transportation demand or shifting it to less energy intensive and more sustainable modes could have a strong impact on the overall success.

CRedit author statement

Karlo Hainsch: Conceptualization, Investigation, Data curation, Model runs, Validation, Visualization, Writing, Funding acquisition..

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Data availability

The data used for the analysis can be found in Hainsch (2022). The repository contains all relevant input data, model code, and result analyses tools which were used for this work.

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